

ABOUT THE TRANSCRIPTIONS OF ETHNONYM TURK IN THE ANCIENT CHINESE WRITTEN SOURCES

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Abstract. *The article, based on Chinese sources and literature, examines Chinese hieroglyphic transcriptions of the ethnonym Turk from different eras. It has been established that the earliest transcription of the ethnonym Turk was the hieroglyph tiek (modern cht. di), the appearance of which dates back to the beginning of the second millennium. The latest transcription of the ethnonym Tuekiuet (modern Tuzhue) appeared in the 6th century. It was transformed from the tribal name Turkkut.*

Keywords: *chinese sources, ethnonyms, Turk, tiek, tieklek, turkkut, tujue, hieroglyphs, ancient reading, transcription, semantics, meaning, etymology, region, Aral Sea, Ordos, Mongolia, Taklamakan Desert, ancient China, Hexi Corridor.*

Introduction. It is important to suggest about the earliest Chinese transcription of the ethnonym Turk. Despite the fact that a large number of scientific works are devoted to the study of the history of the Turkic peoples, there are still many controversial issues that require the establishment of historical truth. First of all, this concerns the definition of the early Chinese transcriptions of the ethnonym Turk from the terms used by Chinese in relation to Turks. Clarification of this issue is important for the correct understanding and assessment of many historical events in the history of Turks.

Definitely, in the absence of local written sources on the history of ancient Turks, Chinese written monuments remain an important source in the study of this issue. Unfortunately, these monuments are not available to everyone. Russian-speaking researchers mainly use the translations of N. Ya. Bichurin and European scientists. There is no doubt that these translations have important scientific value. However, as it seems to us, these translations did not provide all the information from Chinese sources, and many ethnonyms, toponyms, hydronyms and personal names written in hieroglyphs were left without the necessary comments. In most cases, when translating Chinese texts, modern readings of hieroglyphs were used, which made it difficult to find the etymology of many ethnic and geographical names. In many translations, the hieroglyphs that recorded ethnonyms, toponyms, hydronyms and personal names were not given. All this led researchers to misunderstand some important messages from ancient Chinese sources. First of all, such erroneous interpretations include ancient Chinese transcriptions of the ethnonym Turk.

Moreover, starting in 2006, in connection with the beginning of the translation into Uzbek of individual passages from Chinese collection of the history of 24 dynasties "Ershisi shi" ("24 stories"), we paid special attention to clarifying such issues. The results of the work done in this direction are reflected in detail in two monographs published by us: "From the History of the Ancient Turks" (270 pages) and "Information from Ancient Chinese Sources on the Ethnic History of Central Asia" (358 pages).

In the given research there was considered the possibility to briefly dwell on the results of the study of ancient Chinese transcriptions of the ethnonym Turk based on Chinese sources and literature. It should be emphasized that in the article we do not set ourselves the task of conducting

a comparative analysis of the messages of Chinese sources and the conclusions of Chinese scientists with the views of European and Russian-speaking authors. Such work will be able to be carried out in the future by young historians, since this does not require in-depth knowledge of Chinese language.

The study and analysis of ancient readings of hieroglyphs revealed the most ancient Chinese hieroglyphic transcription of the ethnonym Turk. This hieroglyph is di (di 狄, also read ti [36. Since 1994]), in modern reading.

Previously most historians noted that this ethnonym or hieroglyph was used in relation to the early Turkic tribes that lived north of ancient China. The Chinese etymological and encyclopedic dictionaries indicate that the hieroglyph di is a common Chinese name for the tribes that lived north of ancient China. In particular, the etymological dictionary "Ciyuan" ("Origin of Words") states: "Di (di 狄) is a common name for the small peoples who lived north of our state 狄 - 對我國北方地區少數民族的泛稱) [36. Since 1994]. The large 8-volume dictionary "Hanyu Dazidian" states: "Di (di 狄) is the name of the ancient people of our state" (狄 - 我國古代民族名) [26. Vol. 2. P. 1337]. The fundamental collective work "Zhongguo minzu shi" ("History of the Peoples of the PRC"), edited by the famous Chinese scholar Wang Zhonghan, states: "In the middle plain, the ancient Chinese called the northern peoples by the word di" [15 P. 133].

It is clear from these comments, the hieroglyph di is an ethnic name used by the ancient Chinese in relation to their northern neighbors. However, the modern reading of the hieroglyph di does not allow us to establish that it was a Chinese transcription of the ethnonym Turk. In ancient times, the hieroglyph di (狄) was pronounced tiek. This gives reason to believe that this hieroglyph (word) was used by ancient Chinese as a transcription of the ethnonym Turk.

Besides that, the use of the hieroglyph tiek / di (狄) to transcribe the ethnonym Turk was not accidental. In ancient times, this hieroglyph was used to mean power [15. P. 134]. In ancient Chinese, it appeared as a result of the addition of two signs - (petroglyphs) denoting a large animal (quan 犴) and fire (huo 火). Together, both parts, in the understanding of ancient people, meant strength and power.

In the collection of commentaries by ancient authors "Er-ya" (Er-ya – "Explanation of ancient hieroglyphs"), compiled during the 11th–2nd centuries BC, it is indicated that the hieroglyph tiek / di (狄) was originally used to denote cattle or mountain bulls, which in the minds of ancient people were symbols of strength and power [15. P. 133].

In the dictionary of the ancient Turkic language, the word türük or türk means strong, mighty, great [8. P. 599, 611]. A similar explanation of this word is given in the dictionary of the ancient Uyghur language [38. P. 184]. Analyzing the various opinions on the meaning of the ethnonym türk existing in the scientific literature, the Taiwanese scholar Lin Wenshian came to the conclusion that such a meaning actually took place. [17. P. 37]. The Russian scholar Lev Gumilyov also wrote: "The word "Turk" itself means "strong, sturdy" [9. P. 28]. The Uyghur scholar Turgun Almas was of the same opinion [37. P. 177].

What is more important, based on the data presented, we came to the conclusion that the hieroglyph chosen by ancient Chinese to transcribe the ethnonym Turk conveyed not only its pronunciation, but also its meaning.

Regarding the information about the time of the appearance of the first Chinese transcription of the ethnonym Turk it should be suggested that there are different opinions in the

scientific community about the time of the beginning of the use of the hieroglyph *tiek* / *di* as a Chinese transcription of the ethnonym Turk. For example, a group of such Chinese scientists as Lin Gan, Anwar Baytur, Khairinisa Sydyk and others noted that the tribes called *di* in ancient written monuments became known to the ancestors of Chinese during the period when they began to call themselves *xia* (夏) or *huaxia*» [26. T. 2. C. 869]. The ethnonym *Shia* (*shia* 夏, in modern Chinese transcription *Xia*) appeared after the ancestors of Chinese from the modern Henan province moved to the region (*Xia* 夏), located in the southwest of Hebei, and formed the first kingdom. In ancient times, the hieroglyph *xia* was used to mean great, powerful. Therefore, the ancestors of Chinese (Han), having created their first kingdom, called it and themselves by this word. Later, the inhabitants of this kingdom also called themselves *huaxia* (in Modern Chinese transcription *huaxia* 华夏 / 华夏 - cultural or prosperous *xia*) [26. Vol. 2. P. 869]. The time of existence of this kingdom dates back to 2205-1766 BC. Its territory included the modern Chinese province of Henan and surrounding areas.

Certainly, another group of Chinese scholars believes that the time of the appearance of the ethnonym *tiek* in Chinese sources dates back to the 6th century BC, i.e. to the middle of the Spring and Autumn Period (770–476 BC) [26. Vol. 2. P. 869]. Our research allows us to conclude that the point of view of the first group of Chinese scholars corresponds to historical reality. The following arguments can be given in favor of this conclusion:

1. Referring to the commentary of ancient Chinese historians, the hieroglyphic dictionary “*Hanyü dazidian*” notes that in the *Xia* Dynasty (2140–1766 BC.) “the *Yi* tribes (eastern neighbors of Chinese) and the *Tiek* (*di* – Turks) began to appear on the territory of ancient China (*Zhongguo*, which means the Middle Kingdom)” [26. Vol. 2. P. 869; 15. P. 71–72]. Consequently, already at the beginning of the second millennium BC the Turks and Chinese had contacts with each other.

One of the authoritative scientists of the 18th–19th centuries *Duan Yuzai* (1737–1815), commenting on ancient texts, wrote that the *Xia* people “differed from the neighboring peoples of *tiek* (*di* 狄) in the north, *mea* (he 貉 [– means badger] – in the northeast, *yi* (ancient *yiey* 夷) – in the east, *chiang* (ancient *kiang* 羌) – in the west...” [26. Vol. 2. P. 869].

It is worthy to note that in this case, the name *yi* / *yiey* refers to the tribes that lived on the territory of Shandong Peninsula (Shandong 山東 / 山东). The ethnonym *chiang* / *kiang* (羌) arose more than 3.5 thousand years ago as a Chinese generalized name for ancient tribes that lived on a long strip from Pamir to Ordos, including the valleys along the southern and eastern edges of Taklamakan Desert in East Turkestan, the modern province of Qinghai (*Kukunor*) and the coast of the upper reaches of the Yellow River. According to available information, the ethnonym *qiang* / *kiang* is transformed from the word *yang* (羊 - ram, sheep) [2. Vol. 3. P. 2675; 15. P. 123]. The *qiang* / *kiang* themselves did not use this name, but called themselves *ri-mian* (日綿 - ancient *riet-mian*) and *ri-ma* (日馬 / 日马 - ancient *riet-mea*). The time of the appearance of the *kiang* / *chiang* tribes in the indicated regions is also not reported in Chinese written sources. The remains of ancient people who lived 5-6 thousand years ago found in the territory of East Turkestan [10. Pp. 250-256] give reason to believe that the origin of *qiang* / *kiang* could be connected with them. [For details, see: 12. Pp. 71-106].

2. In “*Jaguwen*” inscriptions on stones and animal bones from the Yin period (1324–1122 BC) were found that contained a petroglyph (a hieroglyph in the form of a picture) *tiek* (狄) [14.

P. 51]. In the written monument “Shangshu” the ethnonym pek-tiek / bei-di (北狄) [14. P. 51] is found, which means northern Turks. As is known, this monument is a collection of statements by the rulers of the Xia dynasty (2140–1766 BC), Shang (1711–1066 BC) and Shi-Zhou (1066–770 BC) and descriptions of events during the periods of these kingdoms. The messages contained in the source show that the Turks (tiek / di) and the northern Turks (pek-tiek / bei-di) had connections with Chinese kingdom of Xia. The habitat of the Turks (tiek / di) is localized in the north and west of the territory of ancient China, and the northern Turks (pek-tiek / bei) are on the Ordos.

The above information gives grounds to believe that the ethnonym tiek / di was used by ancient Chinese already in the 21st–17th centuries BC, and that a people under this name existed even earlier.

3. According to Wang Guowei (王国维, pseudonym Guan Tang / Guan Tang 观堂 – 1877–1927), who studied ancient written monuments, the character tiek / di is found on metal objects from the Western Zhou (1060–771 BC) and Eastern Zhou (770–256 BC) periods. Studying the inscriptions on these objects, he came to the conclusion that “the people mentioned in the sources under the name tiek / di are the people of the western lands (Situ / Shitu 西土), in [ancient] poems they were called Shia-reei-kia), which meant “the Turks of the lands of the far east” [15. Pp. 133–134].

4. As indicated above, all Chinese reference works unanimously note that tiek / di is the general name of the people who lived in the north and west of ancient China. It is also indicated that sometimes the northern part of tiek / di was called pek-tiek / bei-di (北狄) [26. V. 2. P. 1337]. In the special issue “History of China” of the Great Chinese Encyclopedia it is indicated that “there were very many tribes within tiek / di 狄” [29. P. 105].

After studying the most ancient written monuments available to us, it can be summarized that the data provided in the aforementioned dictionaries is beyond doubt. The ancient tribes called Turk (tiek / di 狄) occupied a vast territory, including regions located in the north and west of ancient China.

5. According to ancient Chinese sources, at the end of the second millennium BC, the Chinese also used the hieroglyph tiauk (modern reading di 翟) to transcribe the ethnonym Turk, which appeared through the addition of the hieroglyphs yü (羽 - bird feather) and zhui (隹 - bird with a short tail, falcon), the first on top of the second. The use of a new hieroglyph to transcribe the ethnonym Turk was also not accidental, since the ancient Turks had a custom of attaching bird feathers to their headdresses.

The work “Guben zhushu jinian” (古本竹书 – “Chronological records in the ancient texts of bamboo books”) provides information that the second Zhou ruler Chengwang (成王 – 1063–1025 BC) attacked the western kuai-rivem (gui-rong 鬼戎) tribes and captured 20 tiauk (di 翟) rulers [16. P. 8]. This message indicates not only that the character tiauk (di 翟) was used at the end of the second millennium BC as a synonym for the character tiek / di (狄), but also that kuai-rivem (gui-rong 鬼戎) and tiauk / di (翟) were different names for the same people. This conclusion is supported by other reports. For example, the Hanyu Dazidian dictionary states that during the Zhou Dynasty (11th–7th centuries BC), the character tiauk/di 翟 was used as a synonym for the character tiek/di (狄) [26. Vol. 5. P. 3350]. Excerpts from the works of ancient authors are also cited to confirm this thesis. Thus, in the commentary of Lu Deming (550–630), it is noted that

“at the very beginning, tiek/di (狄) was used instead of tiauk/di (翟)” [26. Vol. 5. P. 3350]. The scholar of the Manchu Qing Dynasty (清) Duan Yuzai (1735–1815) noted in his comments that “tiauk/di翟 and tiek/di狄 are the names of the same people” [26. Vol. 5. P. 3350]. The famous scholar of the end of the reign of the same dynasty, Jun Sheng, wrote that the character tiauk/di (翟) began to be used as a synonym for the ethnonym tiek/di (狄) comparatively later [26. Vol. 5. P. 1337].

The ethnonyms tiek / di (狄) and rivem-tiek / rong-di (戎狄) are more often found in the work “Zuo zhuan” (“The Narrative of Zuo Qiuming”), and tiauk / di (翟) - “Shiji” (Shiji - “Historical Notes”). As is known, the first work was written in the 5th century. BC e. [7. Preface. P. 6], and the second – in 104–91. BC e. [23. S. 149, 151, 188].

6. In the first half of the first millennium, the tiek/di (狄) Turks were strong and had active relations with ancient China. Written monuments of that time report their numerous conflicts with the Chinese [7. P. 208].

According to the opinion of a group of Chinese scientists Lin Gan, Anwar Baitur and Khairinisa Sydyk, “the tiek/di (狄) tribes entered the historical arena at the same time as the Xia or Huaxia tribes in China (Zhongguo)” [7. P. 208]. The Chinese themselves believe that they have at least 5 thousand years of history, therefore, the Turkic peoples had the same ancient history.

7. Along with the above-mentioned messages, ancient Chinese written monuments also contain information that the ancestors of the Turks (tiek / di 狄), including the Huns (Xiongnu, ancient chr. kunna), were the people of the land of the sun (gui-fan 鬼方, ancient chr. kivey-pivang). It should be noted that the hieroglyph kivei / gui (鬼) was used by the ancient Chinese to transcribe the word kyun (sun), and piwang / fang (方) - to designate the countries located around ancient China.

On historical maps compiled by Chinese scholars under the guidance of a major expert in the ancient Chinese language Guo Moruo (Guo Moruo 郭沫若 - 1892-1978), the habitats of the kivei-piwang (gui-fang 鬼方) are localized in the territory of Ordos [32. P. 11–12].

The work “Shan-hai-jing” (山海经 – “Treatise on Mountains and Seas”), compiled in the 5th–3rd centuries BC, contains records that during the Shang (商) kingdom, i.e. in 1766–1402 BC, the kivei-piwang (gui-fang – people of the country of the sun) were engaged in cattle breeding in the eastern part of Tangri-tag (Tien Shan) [24. P. 6].

In East Turkestan, in the Taklamakan Desert, dozens of well-preserved dried human mummies were discovered under the sands, various stone, metal objects and pieces of fabric, the age of which ranges from 4 to 6 thousand years [20. Pp. 70, 162; 30. Pp. 28–29, 42; 31. Pp. 88–101]. An ancient cemetery with an area of 1,500 square meters was found near Lake Lop Nor [10. Pp. 263–264], which confirms the existence of a developed non-Chinese culture in the west of ancient China. In terms of facial type, the local inhabitants were Caucasians and differed greatly from the ancient Chinese.

There are references in Chinese written sources to the fact that the early Turks (tiek / di), including the Huns (Kyunna / Xiongnu), were not Mongoloid [12. Pp. 199–202]. Mongoloid features were acquired after contacts between the eastern parts of the early Turks, including the Huns, and the tribes living in the areas north and east of the modern city of Beijing.

According to changes in the geology of the earth, about 10-12 thousand years ago major climatic changes took place here. As a result of the slow rise of the Himalayan mountain system, the area of the Taklamakan Desert was constantly expanding. Archaeological excavations of the last two centuries show that at least 30 cities and settlements located in the south of the desert were buried by sand 2.5-3 thousand years ago. Some of them moved into the desert almost 150 km from its modern borders, and some - 20-50 km. [22. P. 494-498]. This climate change naturally caused the migration of residents towards the nearest green zones: to the north – to the valleys of the Tangritaga Mountains (Tien Shan) and to the east to Kukunor (modern Qinghai), the Hexi Corridor and Ordos.

8. In ancient inscriptions on stones and animal bones, there is a hieroglyphic sign, the reading and meaning of which is not included in Chinese dictionaries and remains controversial. Graphically, it depicts the sun and the earth, their connection in a certain space. Perhaps the ancestors of the early Turks, whose beliefs were associated with Heaven (Tangri) and the sun, used it as an image of a totem (coat of arms) and called it "kyun" or "gyun".

The following assumption can be made based on the fact that the Huns called themselves kyun, neighbors pronounced their self-name as gyun, hun, kyun, and the ancient Chinese - xun, yun, hun, xunnu. In Chinese sources of an earlier period, there are about 35 forms of writing the name of the Huns in different hieroglyphs. 19 of them convey the ancient pronunciation of the self-name of the Huns with one, the rest - with two hieroglyphs [12. Pp. 47-167, 353-354].

The above information gives reason to assert that the Turks existed long before the first transcription of the ethnonym Turk appeared in ancient Chinese written monuments. At the same time, reports about the ancestors of the early Turks (tiek / di) give rise to a new question - when and where did the people of the land of the sun (kivei-piwang / gui-fang) exist.

On historical maps compiled by Chinese scholars under the guidance of the great expert on the ancient Chinese language Guo Moruo (郭沫若 – 1892-1978), the location of kivei-piwang / gui-fang (鬼方) is localized in the territory of Ordos [32. P. 11–12]. Chinese historians, whose research is based on ancient Chinese written monuments and archaeological materials, claim that the origin of the people of the land of the sun (kivei-piwang/gui-fang), the early Turks, called tiek/di, the Huns and the Kyanns (Qiang) had connections [15. P. 135; 12. P. 102-107].

9. Information has also been revealed that the origin of kivei-piwang/gui-fang (residents of the land of the sun) is related to the Kianns/Qiang. For example, in Du Yu's work Tongdian (Treatise on Laws and Traditions), a fragment of a record from the ancient written monument Guang zhi (广志 – “Expanded Description”) is given, which states that “the kiang / chiang people have a commonality with the pek-tiek / bei-di” (羌与北狄同) [2. Vol. 3. P. 2675].

In one of the commentaries given in the work Shibei (Shiben 世本 – “First Genealogies”), it is stated that “the kivei-piwang / gui-fang were part of the kiang / chiang tribes before the Han times” (鬼方於漢則先零羌是也) [24. P. 7]. This work was compiled in the 10th century, historian Song Zhong (宋衷), and the event being commented on dates back to 770-476 BC.

A fact about this is also given in the work of the famous Chinese historian Wang Guowei (Wang Guowei 王国维, pseudonym Guan Tang 观堂 – 1877–1927) “Guan Tang jilin” (Guan Tang jilin 观堂集林 – “Collected Works of Guan Tang”) [13. P. 584].

According to the Hou Hanshu and Tongdian, during the two Han Dynasties (206 BC to 220 AD), the kiang/chiang tribes inhabited the area from the upper Qizhi River in southwest Ordos

to Turpan in East Turkestan. In Chinese manuscripts of the time, they were referred to as siey-kiang (xi-chiang/shi-chiang), i.e. Western Qiang.

While informing about Tietlæk/tiele – Chinese transcription of ethnonym Turk in the 3rd–5th centuries, it should be suggested that in ancient times, the Chinese ethnonym tiele (tiele, tiele 鐵勒 / 铁勒) was pronounced as t'ietlæk. In the works of N. Ya. Bichurin it is read as – tyele, in L. N. Gumilyov as – Teleut. In reality, tietlæk is a transformation of the ethnonyms tiek-like (狄歷 / 狄历, in modern reading – dili) and t'ïæk-læk (敕勒, in modern reading – chile), the appearance of which dates back to the 3rd century. They are first encountered in “Suishu” (“History of the Sui [Dynasty]”), which was written in 635–637. The modern reading of these hieroglyphs does not allow us to see that they are different readings of the same ethnonym, but their ancient reading allows us to do so. Ancient Chinese historians of different eras used different hieroglyphs with the same or similar pronunciation to transcribe the non-Chinese ethnic name.

In comparison with tiek-liek (dili 狄歷), the ethnonym t'ietlæk (tiele, tiele 鐵勒) arose several centuries later, because before its appearance the Turkic tribes were subjects of the Hunnic Empire. According to ancient Turkic traditions, after unification the name of the dominant tribe became common to all subjects. For this reason, for more than 4 centuries in Chinese sources the majority of Turkic tribes were called shüngnu (ancient künna 匈奴).

The ancient pronunciation of the ethnonyms tiek-like, t'ietlæk resembles the transcription of the word turklik, which was used in the period from the collapse of the Hunnic Empire to the emergence of the Turkic Khaganate on the historical stage. The thesis that tiele is the Chinese name for the Turks was first presented by the Japanese historian Hatake, then confirmed by the Japanese historian Matsuda Hisao (1903-1983). Thus, referring to the article “Connections between 9 Uyghurs and 9 Oguz”, authored by Hatake, Matsuda Hisao wrote: “Hatake determined that tiele is a transcription of Turk. This is truly an outstanding conclusion” [19. P. 271].

Based on the analysis of extensive materials in various languages, Japanese scholars Onedawa Hidemi (Onedawa Hidemi 小野川秀美) and Mori Masao (Mori Masao 護雅夫) believe that dili, chilə, tiele, tujüe are a sound translation of the ethnonym türk [17. P. 38].

At the end of the 19th century, the Danish scholar and linguist W. Thomson, who studied ancient Turkic writing, established that the ethnonyms di, dili, tiele found in Chinese sources are transcriptions of the word “Türkü” or “Türük”, meaning strong [11. P. 63].

Analyzing ancient readings of hieroglyphs, we are convinced that the 3rd–5th centuries. The ethnonym tiele or tiele was pronounced by the Chinese as t'ïæk-læk [15. P. 317], since in dialects of the Chinese language tiek can be pronounced as tiek (tsiek) or diek. In addition, due to the lack of a single transcription rule, Chinese historians often recorded the same foreign name with different identical or similarly pronounced hieroglyphs, which led to the emergence of many different interpretations of non-Chinese ethnonyms.

The histories of the Sui (Suishu) and Zhou (Zhoushu) dynasties report that after the collapse of the Hunnic Empire, tiek-liek or t'ietlæk (tiele, tiele) included 43 tribes that inhabited a vast area from the shores of Bohay (渤海) in the east to the Black and Mediterranean Seas in the west and to Samarkand in the south. Their names are given at the end of this article.

Regarding the transcription of the ethnonym Türk after the 5th century, it should be suggested that in the middle of the 6th century AD, the ethnonym tujüe (突厥) in modern pronunciation appears in Chinese historiography as the name of one of the Turkic tribes. In ancient times, these hieroglyphs were

pronounced as *tuetkiuat*, which was a Chinese transcription of the Turkic word *türk-kut*, meaning “children or sons of the Turks” and was the name of the tribe of the descendants of *Asien* (modern *Ashina*). *N.Ya. Bichurin* transcribed it as “*tyugyu*” and in this form the ethnonym became widespread in Russian-language literature.

From the point of view of semantics, the characters 突厥 *tuetkiuat* / *tujüe* mean “people from the cave”. The use of characters with such a meaning by ancient Chinese historiographers was not accidental. Before moving to *Altai*, this tribe lived for about 70 years in an area surrounded by mountains, located near the modern city of *Urumqi*, near the city of *Jimusa*. The only way to get there was through a cave. Therefore, Chinese sources cite various legends and oral stories about the ancestors of this tribe living in a cave.

In 424–451, the *Türk-qut* (*tuetkiuat* / *tujüe*) tribe, consisting of 500 families, moved to the southern part of the *Altai*, where they submitted to the *Jurchen* kingdom (in Chinese sources *Rouran hanguo* – 394–552), engaged in the extraction and production of iron [1. P. 11709 (831) / 1a /].

The *Türk-qut* tribe consisted of descendants of *Asien* (*Ashina*), whose earliest ancestors lived in the west of the *Aral Sea*, where the *Massagetae* or *Saka* lived. Long before our era, the ancestors of *Asien* moved to the upper reaches of the *Yenisei River*, west of *Lake Baikal*, where the *Asiana* and *Asiə-təka* clans (modern *Ashide* 阿史德) were formed. Subsequently, the second clan settled in the *Otukan* (*Ötükan*) region [25. P. 54] on the eastern side of this lake.

During the existence of the *Hunnic Empire*, the *Asien* and *Asietek* clans were subordinate to them, and after its collapse, they experienced a long migration process. At first, with separate parts of the *Huns*, they moved south to the *Hexi Corridor*, then through *Dunhuang*, *Pshamshan* (in Chinese sources *Shanshan*), *Karashahr* and *Turfan* they moved to the *Jimus* area (north of *Urumqi*). The descendants of the *Asieteka* clan remained in the *Hexi corridor* [for more details, see: 11. Pp. 82–114, 271].

A number of Chinese scholars, whose works are of a fundamental nature, note that the *Türk-qut* (*tuet-kiuat* / *tu-jüe*) tribe with the wolf totem considered as an integral part of the Turkic tribes, which in Chinese sources are called *tiek-liek* / *tiele* or *tielə* [14. P. 293; 15. P. 317]

In the middle of the 6th century, the *türk-qut* (*tuet-kiuat* / *tu-jüe*) tribe acted as a unifier of all the Turkic tribes and the creator of a new state, which received the name of the Turkic *Khaganate* (in Chinese sources *Tujüe hanguo* 突厥汗国 - 552-745). After these events, in early medieval Chinese historiography, the name of the *türk-qut* (*tuet-kiuat* / *tu-jüe*) tribe began to be used as a new transcription of the ethnonym *Türk*. This tradition has survived to the present day.

Based on this, many historians have the incorrect idea that the *Turks* appeared in *Altai* in the 6th century. This opinion, in turn, has had a significant impact on the emergence of various erroneous points of view on many issues of the history of *Central Asia*.

Our research, carried out on the basis of studying primary sources in the original with the involvement of the works of Chinese and Japanese authors in Chinese, shows that before the migration of the *Türk-qut* (*tuetkiuat/tujüe*) tribe to *Altai*, its ancestors went through about a thousand-year migration route from the region located in the west of the *Aral Sea* to *Altai* through the territories of *Mongolia*, *Ordos*, the *Hexi Corridor* and the region of eastern *Tangritag* (*Tien Shan*). Therefore, Chinese sources provide various fragmentary information about the habitat of the ancestors of the *türk-qut* (*tuet-kiuat* / *tu-jüe*) tribe [for details, see: 11. Pp. 82–114].

If we inform about ethnonyms used by the ancient Chinese in relation to the Turkic tribes, there should be suggested in Chinese hieroglyphic, encyclopedic, historical and toponymic dictionaries it is indicated that until the 2nd century BC the Turks were called tienglieng (dingling), later they began to be called tiekliiek (dili 狄歷), t'ieklək (chilə 敕勒), and in the 5th–3rd centuries – t'ietlək (tielə, tiele 鐵勒) [35. P. 1707; 28. P. 1382; 36. V. 4. P. 3215].

It is appropriate to note that tieng-lieng / dingling is not a Chinese transcription of the ethnonym Turk, but is a Chinese name used in relation to the Turks.

At the very beginning, the hieroglyph dingling 丁靈 (modern abbreviated spelling 丁灵) was used to write the ethnonym tienglieng, meaning spirit on top. This term was not a transcription of the ethnonym Turk, but conveyed the meaning of their tradition of worshiping Heaven - Tangri. Later, the Chinese began to write this ethnonym with similarly pronounced hieroglyphs: 丁令, 釘灵, 丁零, which led not only to the loss of the oral meaning of the word tienglieng / dingling, but also served as a reason for the emergence of different interpretations. In some cases, the ethnonym tienglieng / dingling was used in relation to the northern part of the ancient Turks.

In this regard, it is appropriate to note that in Chinese sources there is also the ethnonym kautcia-tienglieng (gaoche-dingling 高車丁零 / 高车丁令), which means spirit worshipers using high carts. This term was used by the Chinese in relation to the Turkic tribes of the early Middle Ages. In this regard, the source "Weishu" ("History of the Wei Dynasty") notes that "the Gaoche were initially called tiek-liek (dili 狄歷), in the north they were called t'ieklək (chilə 敕勒), the Chinese called them kautcia-tienglieng (gaoche-dingling 高車丁零)". Later, Chinese court historians, following the path of abbreviation, began to use only the first half of this term - kautcia (gaoche 高車).

Ancient Chinese sources often contain ethnonyms that were used by the Chinese in relation to the early Turks. These primarily include ɣu (hu 胡), yiey (yi 夷), rivem (rong 戎). In historical literature, there are different interpretations of them.

Our study of these ethnonyms showed that they are not transcriptions of the ethnic names of the early Turks, but were purely Chinese names for them. Thus, the hieroglyph ɣu (hu 胡) meant feeble-minded stupid people, and yiey (yi 夷) - barbarians, wild people, riwem (rong 戎, in Russian literature - zhun) - warriors or people on horses. In Chinese sources, the ethnonyms rivem-tiek (rong-di 戎狄), tiek-rivem (di-rong 狄戎) are also often encountered, which mean Turkic cavalry.

As it was mentioned above, the ethnonym tiek (di 狄), encountered in Chinese sources, is the oldest Chinese transcription of the ethnonym Turk. The time of its appearance dates back to the period of the 21st–17th centuries BC. The hieroglyph tiauk (di 翟) appeared in these sources at the end of the second millennium BC as a synonym.

In Chinese sources, it is also reported that the ancestors of tiek / di – Turk were people from the land of the sun, whose origin is related to the inhabitants of the western lands. This gives reason to believe that the Turks existed long before meeting the ancient Chinese.

After the collapse of the late Han Empire (Hou Han – 25–220), the ethnonym tiek / di was transformed into tiek-liek (dili 狄歷 / 狄历) and t'iek-lək (chilə 敕勒) – Turklik. The suffix lik is used to indicate belonging to one ethnic group.

In the middle of the 6th century, the tribe tuetkiuat / tujüe acted as a unifier of all Turkic tribes and the creator of a new state, which received the name Turkic Khaganate. In connection

with this event, in early medieval Chinese historiography, the name of the tribe *tuetkiuat* / *tujüe* began to be used as a common Turkic ethnic name, which was later transformed into a new transcription of the ethnonym Turk.

The ethnonym *tuetkiuat* / *tujüe* comes from the Chinese transcription of the tribal name *türk-qut*, meaning "descendants of the Turks". Before the ancestors of the *türk-qut* tribe settled and strengthened in the southern Altai, they went through a long and lengthy migration route from the shores of the Aral Sea through the territories of Mongolia, Ordos, the Hesi Corridor, Turpan, Karashar and the central part of Tangritag (an area located near the modern city of Urumqi) [for details, see: 11.82–114].

For summarizing the above, we note that around the end of the 22nd century BC, for the first time in the history of China, they formed a kingdom called Xia, which existed from 2205 to 1766 BC. Turkic tribes lived nearby in the north and west. The inhabitants of this kingdom, the ancestors of the Chinese (Han), having contacts with them, recorded their ethnic name in the hieroglyphs *tiek* (di 狄) meaning strength, power. However, this does not mean that the bearers of this ethnonym did not exist earlier.

From the end of the second millennium BC, the Chinese began to use another hieroglyph with the reading *tiauk* (di 翟) as a synonym. In the 3rd–5th centuries, to transcribe the ethnonym Turk, Chinese palace historians used the hieroglyphs *tiek-liek* (dili 狄歷 / 狄历), *t'ietlæk* (tiele 鐵勒 / 铁勒), the ancient reading of which shows that they were transcriptions of the word *turklik* (Turks or people of Turkic origin).

In the 6th century, in connection with the strengthening of the *Türk-qut* tribe (*tuetkiuat* / *tujüe* 突厥 - descendants of the Turks) and their creation of a new state through the unification of other Turkic tribes, in Chinese historiography the tribal name began to be used as a new transcription of the ethnonym Turk. This tradition continued after the collapse of the Turkic Khaganate. However, this does not give grounds to assert that the Turks appeared only in the 6th century.

The ethnonyms *yu* (hu 胡 – stupid or feeble-minded people), *yiey* (yi 夷 – barbarians, wild people), *rivem* / *rong* (戎 – horse people, cavalry), *tienglieng* (dingling 丁靈, 丁零, 丁灵 – Tengrilik, sun worshipers), *kautcia-tienglieng* (gaoche-dingling 高車丁零) and *kautcia* (gaoche 高車) found in Chinese sources are Chinese ethnonyms used in relation to the Turks. They cannot be considered as the name of individual parts of the ancient Turks of the Central Asian sub-region.

APPENDIX. List of Turkic tribes in the 3rd–5th centuries. under the general name
Tietlek / *Tele* - *Turklik*

(modern reading of hieroglyphs is given in brackets)

Tribes living on the territory of modern Mongolia:

1. *bukku* – *buk-yu* / *pu-gu* 僕骨,
2. *tungra* – *dung-la* / *tong-luo* 同羅,
3. *Uyghur* – *yi-wai-yat* / *yuan-he*, *yuan-ge* 韋纒,
4. *bayirku*, *boyirfy* – *puat-yia-ku* / *ba-ye-gu* 拔野古,
5. *bærkli*, *bÿrkli* – *fu-la* / *fu-luo* 覆羅, *fu-fo*, *fu-bing* 覆竝,
6. *mchin* – *mong-dien* / *meng-chen* 蒙陳,
7. *turugur*, *turugur* – *t'u-ria-yat* / *tu-ru-ge*, *tu-ru-he* 吐如紇,

8. hun – yuən / hun 渾,
9. izgil – siə-kiet / si-jie 斯結, 思結,
10. Kfursu; hogursu – yok-siat / hu-shüe 斛薛.

Tribe that lived south of the lake Baikal:

11. Tuva – tua-pua / du-bo 都波.

Tribes that lived on the territory of Eastern Turkestan:

12. chibni – siat-biat / qi-bi 契弊,
13. bÿri – bak-lak / bo-luo 薄落,
14. oziy, zhida – ciək-tiet-diet / zhi- yidie 職乙咥,
15. siɸnak, signak – sa-bua / su-po 蘇婆,
16. nak, nak, nag – na-γat / na-he 那曷,
17. ŷɸuz, oguz – u-γu / wu -hu 烏護,
18. qirɸiz, Kyrgyz – γət-kuət / he-gu 紇骨, helichisi 纒里迄斯, jilijisi 吉利吉斯, jüwu 居勿,
jegu 結骨, chigu 契骨, hegesi 纒乞斯, hegasi 轄戛斯, tcilitcisi 乞里乞斯,
19. irtish – yia -diet / ye-die 也咥,
20. unigur – u-niei-γu / yü-ni-hu 於尼護,
21. sir-tardush – siat-yian-da / shüe-yan-tuo 薛延陀 (unification of 2 tribes like sire and tardush),

22. dler, jaruk – diet-lek-rie / die-le-er 咥勒兒
23. zabender, zabinder – ziəp-buan / shi-pan 十槃,
24. turgesh – dat-siat / dachi 達契,

Tribes that lived north of Samarkand:

25. adiz, adiet, hadiet – a-diet, ha-diet, a-di / a-die, he-die, a-di 阿跌, 訶咥, 阿噶,
26. Khajat – γat-dziat / he-jie 曷截,
27. Bulgar – puat-huət / bo-hu 撥忽,
28. Pecheneg, bachaneg – piei-kan / bi-gan 比干,
29. tÿɸoy, kuɸoy, kɸoy – jiu-hai / jü-hai 具海,
30. abushi, bosmil, qipchak – γat-piei-siet / he-bi-shi 曷比悉,
31. Khazar, Burtas – γa-dza / he-cuo 何嗟,
32. svar, Siberia – siat-puat / su-bo 蘇撥, 苏拔,
33. yemak, yemok – yia-muat / ye-mo 也末,
34. goth, goch – iat-dat / ye-da 謁達.

Tribes that lived in the east and west of the Caspian Sea:

35. sarogur, sarigur – siat-lak-kiat / su-lu-jie 蘇路羯,
36. saksin, soksin – səm-sa-ien / san-su-yan 三素咽,
37. mokshÿs, mokshos – mietsivok / mie-ts'iwok (mietsu / mie-cu) 篋促,

Tribes living in the east of the Mediterranean Sea:

38. Circassian – sahuət / sa-huət (sahu / sa-hu) 薩忽,
39. hangar, anggar – en-k'iwet / en-qü, en-chü 恩屈,

40. Alan – a-lan 阿蘭,
41. boshkird – pək-ru / bei-ru 北褥,
42. kutrifur, kutrigur – kiəu-lia-biuk / jiu-li-fu 九離伏,
43. avarhun – wa-huən / wa-hun 嵬昏.

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